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1 The Human Connectome Project

The NIH Blueprint for Neuroscience Research Human Connectome Project (HCP) (1) is in the process of mapping the connections of the adult human brain as completely as possible using the following techniques:

- diffusion tractography,
- functional MRI (fMRI),
- magnetoencephalography (MEG),
- electroencephalography (EEG),
- genetic mapping and expression.

This comprehensive initiative involves two different consortia: the Washington University, the University of Minnesota and Oxford University consortium (WU–Minn HCP) (2) and the Massachusetts General Hospital and the University of California, Los Angeles consortium (MGH–UCLA HCP) (3).

2 Magnetic resonance

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is one of the most important non-invasive imaging techniques in medicine. Its physical basis is the so-called Larmor's precession, the precession of the magnetic moment of an object about an external magnetic field B . It is known that the magnetic moment precesses with an angular frequency given by the Larmor's equation: $\omega = \gamma B$, where γ is a property of the object, called gyromagnetic ratio. Since nuclei and particles with a spin number (I) larger than zero have an associated magnetic moment $\mu = \gamma I$, Larmor's equation applies to them too. When an electromagnetic radiofrequency pulse (RF pulse) is applied with a frequency equal to the precession angular frequency of the particle (condition of resonance), the particle absorbs energy from the RF pulse and then releases the same energy as photons with a frequency equal to ω . If the RF pulse has three spatial gradients, it is possible to localize the source of this emission in a cartesian system of coordinates (4). This is the basis of MRI. Since hydrogen is the most abundant element in the human body and its nucleus (whose spin is $\frac{1}{2}$) has the largest magnetic moment among all stable nuclei, most of the MRI applications are based on the resonance of protons.

2.1 Diffusion tensor MRI

Diffusion tensor MRI (DT-MRI) is a in vivo imaging modality with the potential to generate three dimensional images of highly anisotropic anatomical structures such as nerves, muscles, ligaments, tendons, etc. This method is based on the observation that diffusion of water molecules in tissues is retarded by cell walls and other obstacles so that it happens mainly along the directions of axons, muscle fibres, etc. On the other hand, nuclear magnetic resonance can be used to measure water diffusivity in biological tissues. So we can, at least in theory, draw the axes of anisotropic structures following the diffusion of water molecules along them (5).

2.1.1 The tensor of diffusion

Diffusion in an anisotropic material is described by Fick's first law:

$$\text{Eq. 1} \quad \vec{J}(x, y, z, t) = -D(x, y, z) \vec{\nabla} C(x, y, z, t) = - \begin{bmatrix} d_{xx} & d_{xy} & d_{xz} \\ d_{yx} & d_{yy} & d_{yz} \\ d_{zx} & d_{zy} & d_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \vec{\nabla} C$$

where the matrix D is the *diffusion tensor*, the scalar field $C = C(x, y, z, t)$ is the concentration of spin-labelled protons, and $\vec{\nabla}C$ is its gradient. The *diffusion vector* \vec{J} is measured in $\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{m}^2\text{s}}$, the concentration is measured in $\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{m}^3}$, the elements of D are measured in $\frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{s}}$. The conservation of mass must hold, then if we consider a volume Ω delimited by a surface $\partial\Omega$, than we can write

$$\iint_{\partial\Omega} (\vec{J}(x, y, z, t) \cdot \hat{n}) dx dy = - \iiint_{\Omega} \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} dx dy dz$$

By applying the divergence theorem to the integral on the left hand of the equation we get:

$$\iiint_{\Omega} \text{div} \vec{J}(x, y, z, t) dx dy dz = - \iiint_{\Omega} \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} dx dy dz$$

and since Ω is arbitrary, it must be $\text{div} \vec{J}(x, y, z, t) = - \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t}$ and given Eq. 1 we have

$$\text{Eq. 2} \quad \text{div} [D(x, y, z) \vec{\nabla} C(x, y, z, t)] = \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t}$$

Consider then that

$$\begin{aligned} D(x, y, z) \vec{\nabla} C(x, y, z, t) &= \begin{bmatrix} d_{xx} & d_{xy} & d_{xz} \\ d_{yx} & d_{yy} & d_{yz} \\ d_{zx} & d_{zy} & d_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} d_{xx} + \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} d_{xy} + \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} d_{xz} \\ \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} d_{yx} + \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} d_{yy} + \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} d_{yz} \\ \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} d_{zx} + \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} d_{zy} + \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} d_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow \\ \Rightarrow \text{div} [D(x, y, z) \vec{\nabla} C(x, y, z, t)] &= \left(\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} d_{xx} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x \partial y} d_{xy} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x \partial z} d_{xz} \right) + \\ &+ \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \frac{\partial d_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \frac{\partial d_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \frac{\partial d_{xz}}{\partial x} + \left(\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y \partial x} d_{yx} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} d_{yy} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y \partial z} d_{yz} \right) + \\ &+ \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \frac{\partial d_{yx}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \frac{\partial d_{yy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \frac{\partial d_{yz}}{\partial y} + \left(\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z \partial x} d_{zx} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z \partial y} d_{zy} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} d_{zz} \right) + \\ &+ \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \frac{\partial d_{zx}}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \frac{\partial d_{zy}}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \frac{\partial d_{zz}}{\partial z} \end{aligned}$$

Considering now that for Schwartz's theorem it is $\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x \partial y} = \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y \partial x}$, $\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x \partial z} = \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z \partial x}$, $\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y \partial z} = \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z \partial y}$, it follows that Eq. 2 can be written also:

$$\text{Eq. 3} \quad \frac{\partial C(x, y, z, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} d_{xx} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} d_{yy} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} d_{zz} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x \partial y} (d_{xy} + d_{yx}) + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x \partial z} (d_{xz} + d_{zx}) + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y \partial z} (d_{yz} + d_{zy}) +$$

$$+ \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial d_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial d_{yx}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial d_{zx}}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \left(\frac{\partial d_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial d_{yy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial d_{zy}}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \left(\frac{\partial d_{xz}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial d_{yz}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial d_{zz}}{\partial z} \right)$$

which is the differential equation for diffusion for anisotropic media, also called Fick's second law of diffusion (6). The diffusion tensor is assumed to be symmetric in DT-MRI (7). Why? I haven't found an explanation for this assumption, but consider the case in which we assume that D doesn't change in the volume we are considering (as it seems to be the case in practical applications, where D has a unique value within a voxel), then Eq. 3 becomes:

$$\text{Eq. 4} \quad \frac{\partial C(x,y,z,t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} d_{xx} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} d_{yy} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} d_{zz} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x \partial y} (d_{xy} + d_{yx}) + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x \partial z} (d_{xz} + d_{zx}) + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y \partial z} (d_{yz} + d_{zy})$$

This equation would be the same if, instead of using D , we used its symmetrical component, which is the second matrix on the right hand of the following decomposition of D in its antisymmetric and symmetric components:

$$\text{Eq. 5} \quad D = D^{(as)} + D^{(s)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{d_{xy}-d_{yx}}{2} & \frac{d_{xz}-d_{zx}}{2} \\ -\frac{d_{xy}-d_{yx}}{2} & 0 & \frac{d_{yz}-d_{zy}}{2} \\ -\frac{d_{xz}-d_{zx}}{2} & -\frac{d_{yz}-d_{zy}}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} d_{xx} & \frac{d_{xy}+d_{yx}}{2} & \frac{d_{xz}+d_{zx}}{2} \\ \frac{d_{xy}+d_{yx}}{2} & d_{yy} & \frac{d_{yz}+d_{zy}}{2} \\ \frac{d_{xz}+d_{zx}}{2} & \frac{d_{yz}+d_{zy}}{2} & d_{zz} \end{bmatrix}$$

So, we can always pick a symmetric diffusion tensor such that the differential equation of diffusion has the same value, granted that D doesn't change with x, y, z within the volume we are considering. Another interesting point here is the physical meaning of the antisymmetric component of D . If we consider the vectorial field generated by substituting only $D^{(as)}$ in the Fick's law, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{J}(x, y, z, t) &= -D^{(as)}(x, y, z) \vec{\nabla} C(x, y, z, t) = \\ &= - \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{d_{xy} - d_{yx}}{2} & \frac{d_{xz} - d_{zx}}{2} \\ -\frac{d_{xy} - d_{yx}}{2} & 0 & \frac{d_{yz} - d_{zy}}{2} \\ -\frac{d_{xz} - d_{zx}}{2} & -\frac{d_{yz} - d_{zy}}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \frac{d_{xy} - d_{yx}}{2} + \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \frac{d_{xz} - d_{zx}}{2} \\ -\frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \frac{d_{xy} - d_{yx}}{2} + \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \frac{d_{yz} - d_{zy}}{2} \\ -\frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \frac{d_{xz} - d_{zx}}{2} - \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \frac{d_{yz} - d_{zy}}{2} \end{bmatrix} = \\ &= - \begin{bmatrix} \hat{e}_1 & \hat{e}_2 & \hat{e}_3 \\ -\frac{d_{yz} - d_{zy}}{2} & \frac{d_{xz} - d_{zx}}{2} & -\frac{d_{xy} - d_{yx}}{2} \\ \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{d_{yz} - d_{zy}}{2} \\ \frac{d_{xz} - d_{zx}}{2} \\ -\frac{d_{xy} - d_{yx}}{2} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} \frac{d_{zy} - d_{yz}}{2} \\ \frac{d_{xz} - d_{zx}}{2} \\ \frac{d_{yx} - d_{xy}}{2} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

This is a rotational field around the direction of the vector $\vec{\omega} = -\frac{d_{zy}-d_{yz}}{2} \hat{e}_1 - \frac{d_{xz}-d_{zx}}{2} \hat{e}_2 - \frac{d_{yx}-d_{xy}}{2} \hat{e}_3$, similar to the vector field of velocities of a rigid body that rotates with an angular speed $\vec{\omega}$ (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The component of the vector of diffusion due to the antisymmetric component of the tensor of diffusion is a rotational field.

One might argue that a diffusion orthogonal to the gradient of concentration is not diffusion at all. This leads to the conclusion that $\vec{\omega}$ has to be zero, in other words we have

$$\text{Eq. 6} \quad d_{yz} = d_{zy}, \quad d_{xz} = d_{zx}, \quad d_{yx} = d_{xy}$$

and the diffusion tensor is, in fact, symmetric. *From now on, we assume that D is a symmetric matrix.* But if this is the case, it can be diagonalized with the usual methods of linear algebra (8). Briefly, a symmetric matrix always has three real eigenvalues $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ and a corresponding set of orthonormal eigenvectors $\hat{e}_1, \hat{e}_2, \hat{e}_3$, such that $D\hat{e} = \lambda\hat{e}$ or, equivalently, $(D - \lambda I)\hat{e} = 0$. In order for this homogeneous linear system to have solutions besides the obvious one, its determinant has to be zero:

$$\text{Eq. 7} \quad \det \begin{bmatrix} d_{xx} - \lambda & d_{xy} & d_{xz} \\ d_{xy} & d_{yy} - \lambda & d_{yz} \\ d_{xz} & d_{yz} & d_{zz} - \lambda \end{bmatrix} = 0$$

This is an equation of the third degree whose solutions are the eigenvalues. By substituting the eigenvalues in the linear system $D\hat{e} = \lambda\hat{e}$, we get the corresponding eigenvectors. We can now consider a new system of coordinates, using the eigenvectors to define a new set of orthogonal axes:

$$\begin{aligned} & \xi\hat{e}_1 + \eta\hat{e}_2 + \zeta\hat{e}_3 = x\hat{e}_1 + y\hat{e}_2 + z\hat{e}_3 \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow & \xi(\varepsilon_{1x}\hat{e}_1 + \varepsilon_{1y}\hat{e}_2 + \varepsilon_{1z}\hat{e}_3) + \eta(\varepsilon_{2x}\hat{e}_1 + \varepsilon_{2y}\hat{e}_2 + \varepsilon_{2z}\hat{e}_3) + \zeta(\varepsilon_{3x}\hat{e}_1 + \varepsilon_{3y}\hat{e}_2 + \varepsilon_{3z}\hat{e}_3) = \\ & = x\hat{e}_1 + y\hat{e}_2 + z\hat{e}_3 \Leftrightarrow (\xi\varepsilon_{1x} + \eta\varepsilon_{2x} + \zeta\varepsilon_{3x})\hat{e}_1 + (\xi\varepsilon_{1y} + \eta\varepsilon_{2y} + \zeta\varepsilon_{3y})\hat{e}_2 + \\ & + (\xi\varepsilon_{1z} + \eta\varepsilon_{2z} + \zeta\varepsilon_{3z})\hat{e}_3 = x\hat{e}_1 + y\hat{e}_2 + z\hat{e}_3 \Leftrightarrow \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Eq. 8} \quad \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{1x} & \varepsilon_{2x} & \varepsilon_{3x} \\ \varepsilon_{1y} & \varepsilon_{2y} & \varepsilon_{3y} \\ \varepsilon_{1z} & \varepsilon_{2z} & \varepsilon_{3z} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{1x} & \varepsilon_{2x} & \varepsilon_{3x} \\ \varepsilon_{1y} & \varepsilon_{2y} & \varepsilon_{3y} \\ \varepsilon_{1z} & \varepsilon_{2z} & \varepsilon_{3z} \end{bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix}$$

For the formula above, remember that the inverse of an orthogonal matrix is equal to its transpose. We also have

$$\begin{aligned} & \begin{bmatrix} d_{xx} & d_{xy} & d_{xz} \\ d_{xy} & d_{yy} & d_{yz} \\ d_{xz} & d_{yz} & d_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{1x} \\ \varepsilon_{1y} \\ \varepsilon_{1z} \end{bmatrix} = \lambda_1 \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{1x} \\ \varepsilon_{1y} \\ \varepsilon_{1z} \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow & \begin{bmatrix} d_{xx} & d_{xy} & d_{xz} \\ d_{xy} & d_{yy} & d_{yz} \\ d_{xz} & d_{yz} & d_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{1x} & \varepsilon_{2x} & \varepsilon_{3x} \\ \varepsilon_{1y} & \varepsilon_{2y} & \varepsilon_{3y} \\ \varepsilon_{1z} & \varepsilon_{2z} & \varepsilon_{3z} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{1x} & \varepsilon_{2x} & \varepsilon_{3x} \\ \varepsilon_{1y} & \varepsilon_{2y} & \varepsilon_{3y} \\ \varepsilon_{1z} & \varepsilon_{2z} & \varepsilon_{3z} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

and more generally

$$\begin{bmatrix} d_{xx} & d_{xy} & d_{xz} \\ d_{xy} & d_{yy} & d_{yz} \\ d_{xz} & d_{yz} & d_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{1x} & \varepsilon_{2x} & \varepsilon_{3x} \\ \varepsilon_{1y} & \varepsilon_{2y} & \varepsilon_{3y} \\ \varepsilon_{1z} & \varepsilon_{2z} & \varepsilon_{3z} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{1x} & \varepsilon_{2x} & \varepsilon_{3x} \\ \varepsilon_{1y} & \varepsilon_{2y} & \varepsilon_{3y} \\ \varepsilon_{1z} & \varepsilon_{2z} & \varepsilon_{3z} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \lambda_2 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \lambda_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

which can be written in a more concise way:

$$\text{Eq. 9} \quad \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{1x} & \varepsilon_{2x} & \varepsilon_{3x} \\ \varepsilon_{1y} & \varepsilon_{2y} & \varepsilon_{3y} \\ \varepsilon_{1z} & \varepsilon_{2z} & \varepsilon_{3z} \end{bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} d_{xx} & d_{xy} & d_{xz} \\ d_{xy} & d_{yy} & d_{yz} \\ d_{xz} & d_{yz} & d_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{1x} & \varepsilon_{2x} & \varepsilon_{3x} \\ \varepsilon_{1y} & \varepsilon_{2y} & \varepsilon_{3y} \\ \varepsilon_{1z} & \varepsilon_{2z} & \varepsilon_{3z} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

In what follows we are going to use the symbols below:

$$\text{Eq. 10} \quad P = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{1x} & \varepsilon_{2x} & \varepsilon_{3x} \\ \varepsilon_{1y} & \varepsilon_{2y} & \varepsilon_{3y} \\ \varepsilon_{1z} & \varepsilon_{2z} & \varepsilon_{3z} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \Lambda = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

So, we have found

$$\text{Eq. 11} \quad \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = P \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} = P^T \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} \\ \Lambda = P^T D P \Leftrightarrow D = P \Lambda P^T \end{cases}$$

From a biological standpoint, it is recognized that the highest (in module) eigenvalue and its corresponding eigenvector indicate the main orthotropic direction of the tissue, in other words, its fibre axis (5). How the elements of D are measured in a voxel is beyond the scope of this document and I won't discuss it.

2.1.2 The density probability of diffusion

Let us consider the diffusion tensor of a point x, y, z . Let's assume that it doesn't change with x, y, z and that it is symmetric. By using its principal directions as new coordinates system we can write Fick's second law (Eq. 4) as follows:

$$\text{Eq. 12} \quad \frac{\partial C(\xi, \eta, \zeta, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 C(\xi, \eta, \zeta, t)}{\partial \xi^2} \lambda_1 + \frac{\partial^2 C(\xi, \eta, \zeta, t)}{\partial \eta^2} \lambda_2 + \frac{\partial^2 C(\xi, \eta, \zeta, t)}{\partial \zeta^2} \lambda_3$$

What about the solution of this differential equation? We can start from the unidimensional case, in other words, consider the differential equation

$$\text{Eq. 13} \quad \frac{\partial C(\xi, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 C(\xi, t)}{\partial \xi^2} \lambda$$

It is useful to remember that if we define the Fourier Transform (9) of a function $f(x)$ as follows:

$$\text{Eq. 14} \quad \mathcal{F}[f(x, t)] = F(\alpha) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(x, t) e^{-i\alpha x} dx$$

then we have the important properties:

$$\text{Eq. 15} \quad \begin{cases} \mathcal{F}\left[\frac{\partial f(\xi, t)}{\partial \xi}\right] = i\alpha \mathcal{F}[f(\xi)] \Rightarrow \mathcal{F}\left[\frac{\partial^2 f(\xi, t)}{\partial \xi^2}\right] = -\alpha^2 \mathcal{F}[f(\xi)] \\ \mathcal{F}\left[\frac{\partial f(\xi, t)}{\partial t}\right] = \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}[f(\xi, t)]}{\partial t} \end{cases}$$

If we now apply these results to both members of Eq. 13 we have

$$\begin{cases} \mathcal{F}\left[\frac{\partial C(\xi, t)}{\partial t}\right] = \frac{\partial \mathcal{F}[C(\xi, t)]}{\partial t} \\ \mathcal{F}\left[\frac{\partial^2 C(\xi, t)}{\partial \xi^2} \lambda\right] = -\alpha^2 \lambda \mathcal{F}[C(\xi, t)] \end{cases} \Rightarrow \frac{dF(\alpha)}{dt} = -\alpha^2 \lambda F(\alpha)$$

This is an homogeneous ordinary differential equation of the first order whose solution is

$$\text{Eq. 16} \quad \mathcal{F}[C(\xi, t)] = A e^{-\alpha^2 \lambda t}$$

Consider now the following Fourier transform:

$$\mathcal{F}\left[e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}}\right] = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}} e^{-i\alpha \xi} d\xi$$

Derivation with respect to α gives

$$\frac{d\mathcal{F}\left[e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}}\right]}{d\alpha} = -i \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \xi e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}} e^{-i\alpha \xi} d\xi$$

If we notice now that $\frac{\xi}{2\lambda t} e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}} = -D\left(e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}}\right)$ and by using the method of integration by parts, we can write

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\mathcal{F}\left[e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}}\right]}{d\alpha} &= -2i\lambda t \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\xi}{2\lambda t} e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}} e^{-i\alpha \xi} d\xi = 2i\lambda t \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-i\alpha \xi} d\left(e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}}\right) = \\ &= 2i\lambda t \left[\left(e^{-i\alpha \xi} e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}}\right)_{-\infty}^{+\infty} - \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}} d(e^{-i\alpha \xi}) \right] = -2\lambda t \alpha \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}} e^{-i\alpha \xi} d\xi = -2\lambda t \alpha \mathcal{F}\left[e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}}\right] \end{aligned}$$

We have a differential equation that can be solved by separation of the variables:

$$\frac{dF[\alpha]}{d\alpha} = -2\lambda t \alpha F[\alpha] \Rightarrow \alpha d\alpha = -\frac{dF[\alpha]}{2\lambda t F[\alpha]} \Rightarrow \frac{\alpha^2}{2} + K = -\frac{\ln|F[\alpha]|}{2\lambda t} \Rightarrow F[\alpha] = K e^{-\lambda t \alpha^2}$$

Now, considering the very well-known integral $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-x^2} dx = \sqrt{\pi}$, we can write

$$F[\alpha = 0] = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}} d\xi = 2\sqrt{\lambda t} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\left(\frac{\xi}{2\sqrt{\lambda t}}\right)^2} d\left(\frac{\xi}{2\sqrt{\lambda t}}\right) = 2\sqrt{\pi\lambda t}$$

then we have $K = 2\sqrt{\pi\lambda t}$ and we have proven that $\mathcal{F}\left[e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}}\right] = 2\sqrt{\pi\lambda t} e^{-\lambda t \alpha^2}$ or

$$\text{Eq. 17} \quad \mathcal{F}\left[\frac{e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}}}{2\sqrt{\pi\lambda t}}\right] = e^{-\alpha^2 \lambda t}$$

By comparing Eq. 16 and Eq. 17 we conclude that $\mathcal{F}\left[\frac{C(\xi, t)}{A}\right] = \mathcal{F}\left[\frac{e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}}}{2\sqrt{\pi\lambda t}}\right]$ and then we have

$$\text{Eq. 18} \quad C(\xi, t) = \frac{A}{2\sqrt{\pi\lambda t}} e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{4\lambda t}}$$

If we now move from one dimension to three dimensions, we have that one set of solutions for Eq. 12 is

$$\text{Eq. 19} \quad C(\xi, \eta, \zeta, t) = \frac{ABC}{8\sqrt{\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3 \pi^3 t^3}} e^{-\frac{1}{4t}\left(\frac{\xi^2}{\lambda_1} + \frac{\eta^2}{\lambda_2} + \frac{\zeta^2}{\lambda_3}\right)}$$

The constant ABC can be calculated considering that if M is the total mass present in the volume, it must be

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} C(\xi, \eta, \zeta, t) d\xi d\eta d\zeta &= \mathcal{M} \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{1}{4t}\left(\frac{\xi^2}{\lambda_1} + \frac{\eta^2}{\lambda_2} + \frac{\zeta^2}{\lambda_3}\right)} d\xi d\eta d\zeta &= \frac{8\mathcal{M}\sqrt{\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3 \pi^3 t^3}}{ABC} \Leftrightarrow \\ \Leftrightarrow 8\sqrt{\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3 \pi^3 t^3} &= \frac{8\mathcal{M}\sqrt{\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3 \pi^3 t^3}}{ABC} \Leftrightarrow ABC = \mathcal{M} \end{aligned}$$

So, we have found the solution

$$\text{Eq. 20} \quad C(\xi, \eta, \zeta, t) = \frac{\mathcal{M}}{8\sqrt{\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3 \pi^3 t^3}} e^{-\frac{1}{4t}\left(\frac{\xi^2}{\lambda_1} + \frac{\eta^2}{\lambda_2} + \frac{\zeta^2}{\lambda_3}\right)}$$

This is a solution for the initial condition in which all the mass is initially concentrated in the origin of the coordinates system, in other words the one that fits the initial condition

Eq. 21 $C(\xi = 0, \eta = 0, \zeta = 0, t) \rightarrow \infty$ for $t \rightarrow 0$

Consider now that

$$[\xi \quad \eta \quad \zeta] \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda_3 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} = [\xi \quad \eta \quad \zeta] \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1^{-1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda_3^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \xi & \eta & \zeta \\ \lambda_1 & \lambda_2 & \lambda_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} = \frac{\xi^2}{\lambda_1} + \frac{\eta^2}{\lambda_2} + \frac{\zeta^2}{\lambda_3}$$

Moreover $\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3 = \det \Lambda$. Then we can write Eq. 20 as

Eq. 22
$$C(\xi, \eta, \zeta, t) = \frac{\mathcal{M}}{8\sqrt{\pi^3 t^3 \det \Lambda}} e^{-\frac{1}{4t} [\xi \quad \eta \quad \zeta] \Lambda^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix}}$$

Then, by considering Eq. 11 we have

$$[\xi \quad \eta \quad \zeta] \Lambda^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} = [\xi \quad \eta \quad \zeta] (P^T D P)^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} = [\xi \quad \eta \quad \zeta] P^T D^{-1} P \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} = [x \quad y \quad z] D^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix}$$

This means that the solution of Eq. 12 with the initial condition in Eq. 21 can be written in terms of the diffusion tensor D and of the coordinates x, y, z as follows

Eq. 23
$$\frac{c(x,y,z,t)}{\mathcal{M}} = \frac{1}{8\sqrt{\pi^3 t^3 \det D}} e^{-\frac{1}{4t} [x \quad y \quad z] D^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi^3 2^3 (2^3 t^3 \det D)}} e^{-\frac{1}{2} [x \quad y \quad z] \begin{pmatrix} D^{-1} \\ 2t \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix}}$$

This function gives the number of moles of spin-labelled protons per unit volume in (x, y, z) at time t , divided by the total number of moles. If we multiply it for the unit volume, we obtain the conditional probability that a spin-labelled proton, whose position was the origin of the coordinate system for $t = 0$, reaches the position (x, y, z) at time t . Now, the reader would probably remember (10) that the probability density of a random vector $\mathbf{X} = [X, Y, Z]$ whose elements follow each a normal distribution is

Eq. 24
$$f_{\mathbf{X}}(x, y, z) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi^3 2^3 \det A}} e^{-\frac{1}{2} [x \quad y \quad z] A^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix}} \quad A = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x^2 & \sigma_x \sigma_y \rho_{xy} & \sigma_x \sigma_z \rho_{xz} \\ \sigma_y \sigma_x \rho_{xy} & \sigma_y^2 & \sigma_y \sigma_z \rho_{yz} \\ \sigma_z \sigma_x \rho_{xz} & \sigma_z \sigma_y \rho_{yz} & \sigma_z^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

where A is the covariance matrix of the random vector with the variance and covariance given respectively by

Eq. 25
$$\begin{cases} \sigma_x^2 = \text{Var}[X] = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (x - \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} v f_X(v) dv)^2 f_X(x) dx \\ \sigma_x \sigma_y \rho_{xy} = \text{Cov}[X, Y] = \frac{\text{Var}[X+Y] - \text{Var}[X] - \text{Var}[Y]}{2} \end{cases}$$

By comparison of Eq. 22 and Eq. 24 we conclude that the matrix $2tD$ is the covariance matrix of the probability density $\frac{c(x,y,z,t)}{\mathcal{M}}$. In other words, the spin-labelled proton initially in the origin of the coordinate system, assume at time t a position (x, y, z) with a variance $2td_{xx}$, and so forth.

Figure 2. Univariate centred normal distribution, for increasing values of variance: as the variance σ^2 increases, the curve becomes more flat.

2.1.3 The ellipsoid of diffusion

If we think about the shape of the curve of the univariate normal distribution (Figure 2), we realize that the matrix $\frac{D^{-1}}{2t}$ or its inverse $2tD$ give an idea on how easy is diffusion of spin-labelled protons in each direction of the space. Now, to get a visual representation of the function in Eq. 23 we write

$$\frac{C(x, y, z, t)}{\mathcal{M}} \sqrt{\pi^3 2^3 (2^3 t^3 \det D)} = e^{-\frac{1}{2} [x \ y \ z] \left(\frac{D^{-1}}{2t} \right) \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix}} \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\Leftrightarrow [x \ y \ z] \left(\frac{D^{-1}}{2t} \right) \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = -2 \ln \left(\frac{C(x, y, z, t)}{\mathcal{M}} \sqrt{\pi^3 2^3 (2^3 t^3 \det D)} \right)$$

If we assign an arbitrary constant value to the right hand, let's say 1, we obtain the surface

$$\text{Eq. 26} \quad [x \ y \ z] \left(\frac{D^{-1}}{2t} \right) \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = 1$$

This is an ellipsoid with the centre in $x = 0, y = 0, z = 0$, as it can be better seen if we change the system of coordinates by reducing the ellipsoid to its canonical form:

$$\text{Eq. 27} \quad [\xi \ \eta \ \zeta] \left(\frac{\Lambda^{-1}}{2t} \right) \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} = 1 \Leftrightarrow \frac{\xi^2}{2t\lambda_1} + \frac{\eta^2}{2t\lambda_2} + \frac{\zeta^2}{2t\lambda_3} = 1$$

As an example, this is the mean diffusion tensor within a voxel of a pork-lion sample with the fibres displaced in the x-z plane, with angle of 41° with respect to the x axis:

$$D = \begin{bmatrix} 0.9761 & 0.0278 & -0.0748 \\ 0.0278 & 0.9529 & -0.0106 \\ -0.0748 & -0.0106 & 0.9653 \end{bmatrix} 10^{-5} \frac{cm^2}{s}$$

Figure 3. Diffusion ellipsoid for a voxel of muscular tissue: the blue axis is the direction of the fibres of the sample, the black axes are the laboratory coordinates, the axes ξ, η, ζ are the principal directions of the diffusion tensor. The main eigen value is the one associated to the ζ axis and it is almost aligned with the fibre axis.

We indicate x, y, z the laboratory coordinates, while ξ, η, ζ are the principal directions of the diffusion tensor with respect to its eigenvalues $\lambda_1 = 0.89341, \lambda_2 = 0.94756, \lambda_3 = 1.05333$. The ellipsoid is plotted in Figure 3 and you can see that its principal direction with the main eigenvalue (ζ) is the one with the best alignment with the fibre direction (the blue axis). What follows is the script I have used to plot Figure 3.

```
% file name = diffusion_tensor
% date of creation = 02/02/2021
% it plots the ellipsoid of diffusion, given the tensor of diffusion
% the ellipsoid is plotted in its canonical space, then the original
% coordinate system is also plotted
clear all
% tensor of diffusion
D (1,1:3) = [0.9761 0.0278 -0.0748];
D (2,1:3) = [0.0278 0.9529 -0.0106];
D (3,1:3) = [-0.0748 -0.0106 0.9653];
% eigenvalues and eigenvectors
[V, lambda] = eig (D)
% is it normalized?
for k=1:3
    V(1,k)^2+V(2,k)^2+V(3,k)^2
endfor
```

```

% transpose of V
Vt = inv(V)
% is it normalized?
for k=1:3
    Vt(1,k)^2+Vt(2,k)^2+Vt(3,k)^2
endfor
% it plots the ellipsoid in canonical space
figure (1)
ellipsoid (0, 0, 0, lambda(1,1), lambda(2,2), lambda(3,3), 20)
pbaspect ([1, 1, 1])
l_m = max( [abs(lambda(1,1)),abs(lambda(2,2)),abs(lambda(3,3))] )
axis ([-2.8*l_m, 2.8*l_m, -2.8*l_m, 2.8*l_m, -2.8*l_m, 2.8*l_m])
xlabel ('\bf\fontsize{10}10^{-5}cm^2/s')
ylabel ('\bf\fontsize{10}10^{-5}cm^2/s')
zlabel ('\bf\fontsize{10}10^{-5}cm^2/s')
hold on
% print x,y,z axes
plot3 ([0,2.5*l_m*Vt(1,1)],[0,2.5*l_m*Vt(2,1)],[0,2.5*l_m*Vt(3,1)],'-k','LineWidth',2)
text (2.7*l_m*Vt(1,1), 2.7*l_m*Vt(2,1), 2.7*l_m*Vt(3,1), '\sl\fontsize{16}x')
hold on
plot3 ([0,2.5*l_m*Vt(1,2)],[0,2.5*l_m*Vt(2,2)],[0,2.5*l_m*Vt(3,2)],'-k','LineWidth',2)
text (2.7*l_m*Vt(1,2), 2.7*l_m*Vt(2,2), 2.7*l_m*Vt(3,2), '\sl\fontsize{16}y')
hold on
plot3 ([0,2.5*l_m*Vt(1,3)],[0,2.5*l_m*Vt(2,3)],[0,2.5*l_m*Vt(3,3)],'-k','LineWidth',2)
text (2.7*l_m*Vt(1,3), 2.7*l_m*Vt(2,3), 2.7*l_m*Vt(3,3), '\sl\fontsize{16}z')
hold on
% print xi,eta,zeta axes
plot3 ([-2*l_m,2*l_m],[0,0],[0,0],'-r','LineWidth',2)
text (2.2*l_m, 0, 0, '\sl\fontsize{16}{\xi}')
hold on
plot3 ([0,0],[-2*l_m,2*l_m],[0,0],'-r','LineWidth',2)
text (0, 2.2*l_m, 0, '\sl\fontsize{16}{\eta}')
hold on
plot3 ([0,0],[0,0],[-2*l_m,2*l_m],'-r','LineWidth',2)
text (0, 0, 2.2*l_m, '\sl\fontsize{16}{\zeta}')
hold on
% plot fibres axis
alpha = -41*pi/360;
vector(1,1) = cos(alpha);
vector(2,1) = 0;
vector(3,1) = sin(alpha);
f_a = Vt*vector
plot3 ([-2.6*f_a(1),2.6*f_a(1)],[-2.6*f_a(2),2.6*f_a(2)],[-2.6*f_a(3),2.6*f_a(3)],'-b','LineWidth',2)
text (-2.7*f_a(1), -2.7*f_a(2), -2.7*f_a(3), '\sl\fontsize{12}fibre axis')

```

2.1.4 In vivo fiber tractography

The parametric equations of a generic curve γ in space (Figure 4) can be written

$$\text{Eq. 28} \quad \gamma: \begin{cases} x = x(t) \\ y = y(t) \\ z = z(t) \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} x = \rho(t) \sin \varphi(t) \cos \theta(t) \\ y = \rho(t) \sin \varphi(t) \sin \theta(t) \\ z = \rho(t) \cos \varphi(t) \end{cases}$$

where t is a generic parameter: for instance, if γ is the trajectory of a particle in space, the parameter t can be the time at which the particle occupies the position $x(t), y(t), z(t)$.

Figure 4. A curve in space, with its generic point P defined by the polar coordinates ρ, θ, φ or the cartesian coordinates $x = \rho \sin \varphi \cos \theta, y = \rho \sin \varphi \sin \theta, z = \rho \cos \varphi$. The unit vector tangent to the curve is \hat{t} , while \hat{n} is the normal unit vector that points the centre of the osculating circumference to γ in P .

The length of the curve from the point $P(t_0)$ to the position $P(t)$ is given by (11):

$$\text{Eq. 29} \quad s(t) = \int_{t_0}^t \sqrt{\left(\frac{d\xi(t)}{dt}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{d\eta(t)}{dt}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{d\zeta(t)}{dt}\right)^2} dt$$

By considering the inverse of this function, we have $t = t(s)$ and by substituting it in Eq. 27 we have a new parametric representation of γ :

$$\text{Eq. 30} \quad \gamma: \begin{cases} x = x(s) \\ y = y(s) \\ z = z(s) \end{cases}$$

In this representation, the tangent unit vector has a particularly simple expression:

$$\text{Eq. 31} \quad \hat{t}(x(s), y(s), z(s)) = \frac{dx(s)}{ds} \hat{e}_1 + \frac{dy(s)}{ds} \hat{e}_2 + \frac{dz(s)}{ds} \hat{e}_3$$

In the present discussion, we assume that $\hat{t}(s)$ is given by the eigenvector \hat{e}_1 of the diffusion tensor in $P(s)$ that is associated with the eigenvalue with the biggest module (λ_1). Since \hat{e}_1 gives the orientation of the fibers of the tissue in P , this method leads to a curve γ that follows the trajectory of the fibers (12). How can we determine γ by knowing the vectorial function $\hat{t} = \hat{t}(s)$? The reader has probably recognized that Eq. 31 can be seen as a first-order system of three differential equations with respect to $x(s), y(s), z(s)$:

$$\text{Eq. 32} \quad \begin{cases} \frac{dx(s)}{ds} = \tau_x(x(s), y(s), z(s)) \\ \frac{dy(s)}{ds} = \tau_y(x(s), y(s), z(s)) \\ \frac{dz(s)}{ds} = \tau_z(x(s), y(s), z(s)) \end{cases} \quad \text{with} \quad \begin{cases} x(0) = x_0 \\ y(0) = y_0 \\ z(0) = z_0 \end{cases}$$

where the point $P_0 = (x_0, y_0, z_0)$ is the starting point of γ . This system and its initial condition represent a Cauchy problem, and as such, it has a unique solution. This problem is the analogous of

the one of finding the trajectory of a fluid particle from the knowledge of the stationary flow field (13). It is not obvious how to analytically solve this system, but we can always solve it numerically, using the Runge-Kutta method for instance. This method is briefly introduced in the following paragraph for a single differential equation. We'll then see how to apply it to the system in Eq. 32.

2.1.4.1 Runge-Kutta method for one equation

In this method we approximate the function $x(t)$ with a line whose angular coefficient is an average of three approximations.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{dx(t)}{dt} \cong \frac{x(t + \Delta t) - x(t)}{\Delta t} \\ \frac{dx\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)}{dt} \cong \frac{x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) - x(t)}{\frac{\Delta t}{2}} \\ \frac{dx(t + \Delta t)}{dt} \cong \frac{x(t + \Delta t) - x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)}{\frac{\Delta t}{2}} \end{array} \right. \Rightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{dx(t)}{dt} \Delta t \cong x(t + \Delta t) - x(t) \\ \frac{dx\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)}{dt} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \cong x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) - x(t) \\ \frac{dx(t + \Delta t)}{dt} \frac{\Delta t}{2} \cong x(t + \Delta t) - x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) \end{array} \right.$$

In our case, $\dot{x}(t) = f(t, x(t))$, so we can write

$$\text{Eq. 33} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} f(t, x(t)) \Delta t + x(t) \cong x(t + \Delta t) \\ f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right) \frac{\Delta t}{2} + x(t) \cong x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) \\ f(t + \Delta t, x(t + \Delta t)) \frac{\Delta t}{2} + x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) \cong x(t + \Delta t) \end{array} \right.$$

Now, we approximate the angular coefficient of the tangent to $x(t)$ with an average value given by

$$\text{Eq. 34} \quad \frac{x(t + \Delta t) - x(t)}{\Delta t} \cong \frac{f(t, x(t)) + 4f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right) + f(t + \Delta t, x(t + \Delta t))}{6}$$

where a higher weigh has been given to the slope at the midpoint. Now, considering the first equation in Eq. 33 we can write

$$\text{Eq. 35} \quad f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right) = f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x(t) + \frac{f(t, x(t)) \Delta t}{2}\right)$$

On the other hand, considering the second equation in Eq. 33 we can also write

$$\text{Eq. 36} \quad f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right) = f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x(t) + f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right) \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)$$

Moreover, we have

$$\text{Eq. 37} \quad f(t + \Delta t, x(t + \Delta t)) = f\left(t + \Delta t, x(t) + f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x(t) + f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right) \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) \Delta t\right)$$

So, if we define $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4$ in the following way

$$\text{Eq. 38} \quad \begin{cases} \lambda_1 = f(t, x(t)) \\ \lambda_2 = f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x(t) + \lambda_1 \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) \\ \lambda_3 = f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x(t) + \lambda_2 \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) \\ \lambda_4 = f(t + \Delta t, x(t) + \lambda_3 \Delta t) \end{cases}$$

we can write Eq. 34 as follows

$$\text{Eq. 39} \quad \frac{x(t+\Delta t) - x(t)}{\Delta t} \cong \frac{\lambda_1 + 2f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x(t) + \lambda_1 \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) + 2f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x(t) + \lambda_2 \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) + \lambda_4}{6}$$

where we have used both the expressions found for $f\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x\left(t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right)\right)$. All that said, the *Classic Runge-Kutta method*, also known simply as the Runge-Kutta method, states that we can assume:

$$\text{Eq. 40} \quad x(t + \Delta t) = x(t) + \frac{\lambda_1 + 2\lambda_2 + 2\lambda_3 + \lambda_4}{6} \Delta t$$

As the method named after Euler, this method approximates locally the function $x(t)$ with a line, but in this case, the angular coefficient of the line is an average of the following angular coefficients: λ_1 , which is the angular coefficient of the tangent to $x(t)$ in t ; λ_2 and λ_3 which are approximations of the angular coefficient of the tangent in $(t + \Delta t/2)$; λ_4 , which is an approximation of the tangent in $(t + \Delta t)$. Note that λ_2 is based on the first approximation, λ_3 on the second and λ_4 on the third. Using a symbology suitable for coding, we can write

$$\text{Eq. 41} \quad \begin{cases} \lambda_1^{(i)} = f(t_i, x_i) \\ \lambda_2^{(i)} = f\left(t_i + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x_i + \lambda_1^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) \\ \lambda_3^{(i)} = f\left(t_i + \frac{\Delta t}{2}, x_i + \lambda_2^{(i)} \frac{\Delta t}{2}\right) \\ \lambda_4^{(i)} = f\left(t_i + \Delta t, x_i + \lambda_3^{(i)} \Delta t\right) \\ x_{i+1} = x_i + \frac{\lambda_1^{(i)} + 2\lambda_2^{(i)} + 2\lambda_3^{(i)} + \lambda_4^{(i)}}{6} \Delta t \end{cases}$$

The order in which the equations are written is also the order that the code must follow in their evaluation (14).

2.1.4.2 Numerical determination of the geometrical axis of one fiber

This holds for one differential equation, now we have to adapt this method to the three differential equations in Eq. 32. For the first equation we have:

$$\text{Eq. 42} \quad \begin{cases} \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} = \tau_x(x_i, y_i, z_i) \\ \lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} = \tau_x\left(x_i + \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}\right) \\ \lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} = \tau_x\left(x_i + \lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}\right) \\ \lambda_{4,1}^{(i)} = \tau_x\left(x_i + \lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}\right) \\ x_{i+1} = x_i + \frac{\lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} + \lambda_{4,1}^{(i)}}{6} \Delta s \end{cases}$$

Analogously, for the remaining two equations we have

$$\text{Eq. 43} \quad \begin{cases} \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} = \tau_y(x_i, y_i, z_i) \\ \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} = \tau_y\left(x_i + \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}\right) \\ \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} = \tau_y\left(x_i + \lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}\right) \\ \lambda_{4,2}^{(i)} = \tau_y\left(x_i + \lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}\right) \\ y_{i+1} = y_i + \frac{\lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} + \lambda_{4,2}^{(i)}}{6} \Delta s \end{cases}$$

$$\text{Eq. 44} \quad \begin{cases} \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} = \tau_z(x_i, y_i, z_i) \\ \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} = \tau_z\left(x_i + \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}\right) \\ \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} = \tau_z\left(x_i + \lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}\right) \\ \lambda_{4,3}^{(i)} = \tau_z\left(x_i + \lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}\right) \\ z_{i+1} = z_i + \frac{\lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} + \lambda_{4,3}^{(i)}}{6} \Delta s \end{cases}$$

These 15 equations must be calculated in the following order:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} \tau_x(x_i, y_i, z_i) \\ \tau_y(x_i, y_i, z_i) \\ \tau_z(x_i, y_i, z_i) \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_x\left(x_i + \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}\right) \\ \tau_y\left(x_i + \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}\right) \\ \tau_z\left(x_i + \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}\right) \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \\ &\rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_x\left(x_i + \lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}\right) \\ \tau_y\left(x_i + \lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}\right) \\ \tau_z\left(x_i + \lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}\right) \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \end{aligned}$$

$$\rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{4,1}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{4,2}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{4,3}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_x \left(x_i + \lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2} \right) \\ \tau_y \left(x_i + \lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2} \right) \\ \tau_z \left(x_i + \lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, y_i + \lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2}, z_i + \lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} \frac{\Delta s}{2} \right) \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow$$

$$\rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} x_{i+1} \\ y_{i+1} \\ z_{i+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \\ z_i \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{1,1}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{2,1}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{3,1}^{(i)} + \lambda_{4,1}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{1,2}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{2,2}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{3,2}^{(i)} + \lambda_{4,2}^{(i)} \\ \lambda_{1,3}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{2,3}^{(i)} + 2\lambda_{3,3}^{(i)} + \lambda_{4,3}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} \frac{\Delta s}{6}$$

As an example of application, let's assume that once we have calculated the tensor of deformation for each point of a 3D grid and once we have determined for each point the value of the eigenvector $\hat{\epsilon}_1$ associated with the eigenvalue with the greatest module, we obtain the vectorial field

$$\text{Eq. 45} \quad \hat{t}(x, y, z) \equiv \hat{\epsilon}_1(x, y, z) = \frac{\vec{v} + \vec{\omega} \times \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix}}{\| \vec{v} + \vec{\omega} \times \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} \|} = \frac{\begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\epsilon}_1 & \hat{\epsilon}_2 & \hat{\epsilon}_3 \\ \omega_1 & \omega_2 & \omega_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix}}{\| \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\epsilon}_1 & \hat{\epsilon}_2 & \hat{\epsilon}_3 \\ \omega_1 & \omega_2 & \omega_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} \|}$$

This vectorial field is analogous to the vectorial field of velocity for a rigid body. This has probably very little meaning from a biological stand point, it is just an example of application of the present numerical recipe. In Figure 5 two fibers drawn by applying the numerical method of par. 2.1.4.1 to the vectorial field in Eq. 45. The script I have used to plot the diagram follows.

Figure 5. Reconstruction of two fibers with the numerical method in par. 2.1.4.1 for $\vec{v} = [0,0,1]$, $\vec{\omega} = [0,0,1]$ and the initial conditions (0.5,0.5,0.0) (red fiber) and (0.8,0.8,0.0) (blue fiber).

```
% file name = tractography
% date of creation = 05/02/2021
% it plots the trajectory of a fibre, given a vectorial field of diffusion
```

```

% eigenvector epsilon_1
clear all
% vectorial field
v = [0,0,1];
w = [0,0,1];
ic = [0.5,0.5,0];
delta_s = 0.5;
function v_f = vectorial_field (x,y,z,v,w)
    v_f = v + cross(w,[x,y,z]);
    v_f = v_f/sqrt(v_f(1)^2+v_f(2)^2+v_f(3)^2);
endfunction
% we set the initial conditions for the first fiber
lambda(1:4,1:3)=0.;
x(1) = ic(1);
y(1) = ic(2);
z(1) = ic(3);
% integration for the first fiber
vector = vectorial_field (x(1),y(1),z(1),v,w);
lambda(1,1) = vector(1);
lambda(1,2) = vector(2);
lambda(1,3) = vector(3);
n = 10;
for i=1:n-1
    for k=2:4
        vector = vectorial_field
(x(i)+lambda(k,1)*delta_s/2,y(i)+lambda(k,2)*delta_s/2,z(i)+lambda(k,3)*delta_s/2,v,w);
        lambda(k,1) = vector(1);
        lambda(k,2) = vector(2);
        lambda(k,3) = vector(3);
    endfor
    x(i+1) = x(i)+(lambda(1,1)+2*lambda(2,1)+2*lambda(3,1)+lambda(4,1))*delta_s/6;
    y(i+1) = y(i)+(lambda(1,2)+2*lambda(2,2)+2*lambda(3,2)+lambda(4,2))*delta_s/6;
    z(i+1) = z(i)+(lambda(1,3)+2*lambda(2,3)+2*lambda(3,3)+lambda(4,3))*delta_s/6;
    vector = vectorial_field (x(i+1),y(i+1),z(i+1),v,w);
    quiver3 ( x(i+1),y(i+1),z(i+1),vector(1),vector(2),vector(3),'-k' )
    hold on
endfor
plot3 (x(1:n),y(1:n),z(1:n),'-r','LineWidth',4)
pbaspect ([1, 1, 1])
hold on
% we set the initial conditions for the second fiber
ic = [0.8,0.8,0];
x(1) = ic(1);
y(1) = ic(2);
z(1) = ic(3);
% integration for the second fiber
vector = vectorial_field (x(1),y(1),z(1),v,w);
lambda(1,1) = vector(1);
lambda(1,2) = vector(2);
lambda(1,3) = vector(3);
for i=1:n-1
    for k=2:4
        vector = vectorial_field
(x(i)+lambda(k,1)*delta_s/2,y(i)+lambda(k,2)*delta_s/2,z(i)+lambda(k,3)*delta_s/2,v,w);
        lambda(k,1) = vector(1);
        lambda(k,2) = vector(2);
        lambda(k,3) = vector(3);
    endfor

```

```
x(i+1) = x(i)+(lambda(1,1)+2*lambda(2,1)+2*lambda(3,1)+lambda(4,1))*delta_s/6;  
y(i+1) = y(i)+(lambda(1,2)+2*lambda(2,2)+2*lambda(3,2)+lambda(4,2))*delta_s/6;  
z(i+1) = z(i)+(lambda(1,3)+2*lambda(2,3)+2*lambda(3,3)+lambda(4,3))*delta_s/6;  
vector = vectorial_field (x(i+1),y(i+1),z(i+1),v,w);  
quiver3 ( x(i+1),y(i+1),z(i+1),vector(1),vector(2),vector(3),'-k' )  
hold on  
endfor  
plot3 (x(1:n),y(1:n),z(1:n),'-b','LineWidth',4)  
grid on
```

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